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Abstract

At present, the adjudication of Muslim marital disputes in India is dominated by men, whether through the government recognized Qazi system or non-state fora such as Darul Qaza's popularly known as Shariah Courts. Calls for gender equality and greater representation for Muslim women have led, predictably, not to inclusion in existing institutions but the setting up of exclusively female run institutions such as those run by the Bharatiya Muslim Mahila Andolan and the All India Muslim Women's Personal Law Board. Looking at the existing situation and issues on the ground with regard to marital dispute resolution, this paper highlights further possibilities available for the inclusion of Muslim women therein. It also argues for a more robust legal framework using methods of alternative dispute resolution and the setting up of a government recognized Arbitration Centre through which the full scope of a female Qazi's powers may be realised.

Keywords: Arbitration, Faskh, Female Qazi, Khula, Shariah Court

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I. Introduction

Every few years or so the Indian media eagerly covers a *nikah* involving a female *qazi* (Bhalla, 2022; Salim, 2019) engendering the usual commentary on the status of women in Islam, the problem with Muslims in India and the old favourite, those misogynistic mullahs. So entrenched is the stereotype that it seems to have vanished from public memory that the hoary and venerable Indian seminary *Darul Uloom Deoband* actually stated that Muslim women could become *qazis*. To quote its spokesperson,

Being a Qazi is a matter of expertise, knowledge and training. Any man or woman who fulfils the criteria of knowledge and training can become a Qazi... Women in Islam have all the right to become religious scholars. They can become a Qazi and a Mufti. (Ali, 2016)

Regrettably, while by now the *mullah* stereotype is hardly surprising, it is strange that no commentator goes beyond framing a female *qazi* solemnising / officiating a *nikah* as revolutionary, rare, progressive. None pause to ask what exactly the role of a *qazi* is, who appoints one and what rules govern the operation of *qazis* in India, which is quite a pity, because as this paper argues the real significance of a *qazi* lies not so much in solemnising a *nikah* as in dissolving one. This capacity to dissolve a *nikah* via *faskh* though has long been contested and the source of much of the confusion can be traced to a law enacted a hundred and forty three years ago in colonial India, with grim consequences for generations of Muslim women.

2. The Kazi's Act of 1880

The Kazis Act of 1880 is certainly a very strange sort of law. Even as it enables the government to appoint kazis, Section 4. of the Act goes on to state:

Nothing in Act to confer judicial or administrative powers; or to render the presence of Ka'zi's necessary; or to prevent any one acting as Ka'zi's.—**Nothing herein contained, and no appointment made hereunder, shall be deemed— (a) to confer any judicial or administrative powers on any Ka'zi' or Naib Ka'zi' appointed hereunder; or (b) to render the presence of a Ka'zi' or Naib Ka'zi' necessary at the celebration of any marriage or the performance of any rite or ceremony; or (c) to prevent any person discharging any of the functions of a Ka'zi.** (The Kazis Act, 1880)

The Act of course makes no mention of divorce and dissolution, yet 4(a) is usually interpreted to mean that no *Kazi* derives the power to effect a divorce from the Act. The question of whether dissolution via *faskh* is necessarily an administrative or judicial power or altogether something else has not been resolved even as the enactment of the Dissolution of Muslim Marriages Act

(DMMA) in 1939 has made matters more complicated encouraging the view that the power to dissolve a Muslim marriage via *faskh* lies exclusively with the courts.

The argument that a religiously qualified qazi's power to dissolve a Muslim marriage via *faskh* is inherent by virtue of his position and has remained unaffected by the enactment of the Kazi's Act or the DMMA is yet to be made in the Indian courts. Further 4(c.) could also be used to argue that if dissolution is interpreted to be a customary function of a *Kazi* then the Act cannot be interpreted in a manner that would prevent any person from discharging such a function.

Notwithstanding all the legal nuances it is established practice in India for Muslim women seeking a divorce to approach a *qazi*, whether government-appointed, hereditary, private or religiously qualified/trained working in a well-known *Darul Qaza*. Further qazis across India in addition to solemnising marriages also play a significant role in either negotiating a divorce, drawing up documents such as *talaqnamas* and/or maintaining some sort of register or record of divorce. Judicial decisions over the decades may have made government appointed qazis in particular more wary but they still continue to offer these services. Dissolution of a *nikah* via *faskh* though is predominantly the sole domain of *Darul Qazas / Shariah Courts*, chiefly operated by the All India Muslim Personal Law Board.

In the landmark case of *Vishwa Lochan Madan* the Supreme Court of India put forth its largely favourable view of a *Darul Qaza* stating that it “functions as an arbitrator, mediator, negotiator or conciliator in matters pertaining to family dispute... can be perceived as an alternative dispute resolution mechanism, which strives to settle disputes outside the courts expeditiously in an amicable and inexpensive manner” (*Vishwa Lochan Madan v. Union of India*, 2014).

However, it also said that such *Shariah Courts* ought not to issue verdicts or *fatwas* unless approached and requested to do so by affected individuals and simultaneously stressed that even when issued upon request the *fatwa* would remain a mere opinion that could be ‘ignored’ and also neither *fatwa* nor verdict would have any legal sanction or validity (Redding, 2018). Subsequent judgements by high courts across India have upheld this view (“Qazi can’t pass court like order”, 2022). *Qazis* have in some cases been instructed to stop intervening in matters of divorce and further ordered to stop issuing any kind of decree or certificate granting divorce. The consequences of this are discussed in Section 4. III (iv) and 5.

As things stand, given that currently government-appointed male *qazis* technically have no role to play in Muslim divorce and fulfil no particular

religious criteria, the title and position having become hereditary throughout most of the country, state governments ought to formally amend/enact rules to pave the way for the appointment of female *qazis* at the earliest. Note that government-appointed *qazis* would be responsible only for solemnising marriages, registering them, issuing marriage certificates and maintaining records. Section 3. I and II below explore the significance of such government-appointed female *qazis*.

However keeping in mind the more thorny and vexing legal issues regarding extra-judicial divorce (explained in the following sections) state governments could either appoint special religiously qualified and trained *qazis* to facilitate the dissolution of *nikah* via *faskh* and issue official divorce certificates or set up a Muslim mediation, arbitration and conciliation centre that through the incorporation of an arbitration clause in the *nikahnama* would be empowered to dissolve a *nikah* via *faskh*. In this case, while only religiously qualified and trained Muslim women would be eligible for appointment to the post of government *qazi* permitted to dissolve a Muslim marriage, arbitration would permit a more diverse set of professional Muslim women to participate. Section 6 of this paper details what a Muslim Arbitration centre might look like.

3. Beyond solemnising to dissolution via *faskh*: A Female Qazi and Shariah Court to aspire towards

It is common in India for commentators and politicians alike to cite reforms in Muslim majority countries to buttress their demands for Family Law Reform but they overlook two basic facts. One, the politics and attendant legitimacy of reform in Muslim majority countries where the populace and the governing class share the same faith is sharply distinct from those in a non-Muslim majority country where the Muslim population is a minority and two, the range of possibilities within Islamic Law available to a Muslim minority population is also very different (Furber, 2011).

Consequently, instead of top-down reform where a predominantly non-Muslim legislature seeks either to arrogate to itself the power to codify Islamic Law or bring in a uniform civil code in opposition to the wishes of a significant number of its Muslim citizens, we ought to look to other democratic republics to argue for a more robust form of legal pluralism. **Israel and Singapore for instance have formal *shariah* courts and both have appointed Muslim women to positions that allow them to dissolve *nikahs* (About the Courts, The *Sharia* Courts, n.d.; History, Syariah Court Singapore, n.d.; Jean, 2020; Lidman, 2017). Ideally we should be lobbying for a female *qazi* formally appointed to an official *shariah* court system in a democratic republic.**

However, that seems very unlikely at the moment in India given the precarious position of its Muslim citizens (Mahmudabad, 2020), relentless propaganda about their ‘appeasement’, the misinformed and perhaps deliberate framing of *darul qazas* as parallel courts reinforcing popular prejudice about the imagined anti-national, secessionist tendencies of Muslim citizens and in line with that prejudice the ingrained belief that Muslims only adhere, obey and pledge loyalty to the Quran as opposed to the Constitution of India. Incessant harping on this particular false binary (Quran vs. Constitution) tends to make most people forget that as Indian citizens Muslim women have the constitutional right as much as anyone else to uphold their religious beliefs and practices. This includes their right to draw up a marriage contract as they deem fit and to opt for arbitration to resolve their marital disputes.

Indian courts recognise the essentially contractual nature of Muslim marriage (Amina v. Hassn Koya, 2004) and the ulema are also well versed with concepts of alternative dispute resolution such as arbitration and amicable settlement (*tahkim* and *sulh* respectively) in Islamic law (Wahb, 2023). It is therefore not far-fetched to suggest that the rights available to Muslim women within the shariah could easily be secured within the framework of already existing secular legislation in force in India such as the Indian Contract Act 1872, Family Courts Act 1984, Legal Services Authorities Act 1987, the Arbitration and Conciliation Act 1996 (subsequently amended) and the various provisions for mediation in the Code of Civil Procedure.

4. What the Inclusion of Muslim Women in the process of Marriage & Divorce looks like, the Existing Situation, Issues and Possibilities.

I. Pre-Marital Counselling. Negotiating the Nikahnama.

Given that most Muslim women getting married have scant knowledge of the rights available to them within the shariah and the rights available to female citizens in India, they lack bargaining power when drawing up a *nikahnama*. While they are free to stipulate conditions and negotiate their *mehr* it is rare to find a Muslim woman who has done so. Male family members do the needful and the *nikahnama* is usually a standardized form.

While the format varies from state to state in Telangana owing to the traditions of the erstwhile state of Hyderabad it is a well-established practice even in remote rural areas to use the *nikah* booklets that are printed and distributed by the state government through the *Qazzath* section housed in the State Waqf Board. Government-appointed *qazis* collect the *nikah* booklets for a fixed fee and utilise them. Efforts are on to revamp the *nikah* booklet to widen the scope of rights available to Muslim women and facilitate awareness about the arbitration clause included therein that would enable Muslim couples to opt

for mediation and arbitration before approaching the courts. However these efforts now seem unlikely to bear fruit as the state government has recently taken a stance insisting it does not have the power to compel *qazis* to buy marriage booklets from the State Waqf Board (Mohammed, 2023).

There is undeniably a great deal of resistance to reform, significantly enough not because of religious reasons but deeply entrenched patriarchy masquerading as the preservation of socio-cultural norms, customs and traditions. However there also exists within the Muslim community considerable angst about women approaching police stations, women-run counselling centres and courts and this can be strategically used to build consensus for creating institutions that use methods of alternative dispute resolution and also appointing Muslim women to such institutions.

Further, while there is an immense reluctance to meaningfully intervene, especially legally, in post-marital disputes whether involving domestic violence or matters about maintenance, abandonment and divorce there is quite a lot of enthusiasm all around for pre-marital counselling; *ulema*, activists, *qazis* and the general public seem receptive to the idea.

In such a scenario the appointment of a female *qazi* in a welcoming women-friendly office would be perfect. As part of a mandatory pre-marital counselling session (“Goa govt”, 2021) the female *qazi* could take the couple through the procedure and help negotiate the conditions of the *nikahnama* in addition to handling all the paperwork. Several state governments across India have successful marriage assistance schemes for minorities. Availing benefits under such schemes could be tied to attending mandatory pre-marital counselling, using the services of a female *qazi*, a conditional *nikahnama* and/or compulsory marriage registration to facilitate the adoption of such practices.

II. Officiating the ceremony. Registering the Marriage.

Women often are unaware of the importance of valid legal documents and the need to ensure they have photographs, invitation cards etc. to prove that the marriage did take place. Having a female present to take them through the process would certainly help. Clarifying the age at the time of marriage and whether the bride is under duress or has freely consented would also be easier to ascertain. At the moment all *Qazis* are male, male family members of the bride handle the entire process and it is not considered ‘proper’ for an unmarried Muslim female to access a *Qazi* office. A considerable number of married Muslim women do not even know where their *nikah* booklet is or whether their marriage certificate has been collected from the *Qazzath* section at the Telangana State Waqf Board.

It is rare to have a Muslim marriage registered. State governments ought to take the lead in enforcing the Supreme Court judgement requiring compulsory registration of marriage irrespective of religion (Seema v. Ashwani Kumar, 2006). This would make verification during any subsequent legal/administrative process much swifter and also enable meaningful regulation of polygamy/bigamy. Nothing bars the government of course from appointing Muslim women to the posts of registrars (Adhwaryu, 2022).

At present leave alone a central database (Roy, 2017) in India there exists no registry of Muslim marriages even within the state of Telangana. Individually government appointed and recognised qazis physically store *nikahnama* copies they have overseen in bundles in their offices. They do not use computers, sticking to pen and paper registers. A copy of each *nikahnama* is stored in the *qazi* office, one is sent to the State Waqf Board *Qazzath* section and another is housed in the state archives. Persons who apply for and obtain a marriage certificate would likely have their details entered into the *Qazzath* system but it isn't clear if the government maintains a searchable database. At any rate, *qazis* do not check to see if an individual is already married to more than one person nor does the *nikah* booklet ask Muslim men any questions about prior marriages or extant wives.

There are valid objections to a digitized central registry on grounds of privacy however with new advancements in technology and consequent possibilities such as community-owned data trusts this should not be an impediment. Speaking of privacy interestingly enough it is an essential requirement in Telangana to furnish photocopies of the Aadhar card of the bride, groom and witnesses to the qazi before the *nikah* ceremony. Aadhar is also mandatory to avail the Shaadi Mubarak scheme as well (“State marriage sops”, 2022).

III. Terminating a Muslim marriage

- i. ***Mubarat*** being a mutually agreed upon divorce (Ahmed & Krayem, 2021) is usually negotiated by the couple themselves with the help of family members or with the involvement of a lawyer if a legal agreement is being drawn up and signed to effect the divorce. It is rare to find a document of *mubarat* in the records of *mahila mandals* or other women run counselling centres. There are several possible reasons for this. The most likely is that since the issue is usually settled privately within the home, often amicably, there exists no record.

The other is that owing to lack of legal literacy (whether secular or religious) Muslim women engaged in settling marital disputes are unaware that something called *Mubarat* exists and even though they may actually facilitate the termination of a marriage with the mutual consent of both parties they fail to effect it as such preferring the more well-known method

of *khula*. Lastly official government procedure in the state of Telangana for issuing a divorce certificate does not include the category of *mubarat* therefore for ease of obtaining a document and avoiding bureaucratic hassles individuals involved in the process stick to classifying a divorce as either *khula* or *talaq*.

- ii. **Talaq** traditionally being the prerogative of the husband is generally effected unilaterally by an oral pronouncement or through a written medium. For a Muslim woman the tricky aspect is having some form of evidence to prove that a *talaq* or multiple *talaqs* actually occurred. Over time with the evolving jurisprudence around *talaq* in India, well informed Muslim men with means to draw upon the services of a lawyer or government-appointed *qazi* either effect *talaq* through written notices over a duration of time or via a formal *talaqnama*, usually with a cheque or demand draft attached covering the amount of maintenance due for the *iddat* period and *mehr* amount, if any, unpaid so that they will not be held liable to pay any further maintenance.

It is unusual though not entirely unheard of to have Muslim women involved in the process of terminating a marriage via *talaq*. Whether the couple is living together or apart as long as husband and wife are still communicating and showing up to counselling sessions, Muslim women involved in resolving the dispute may convince the husband to pronounce a *talaq* on the premises of the counselling centre in front of a mufti or accompany the couple to a *qazi's* office to ensure that the *talaq* is recorded in writing with the signatures of witnesses.

Generally though Muslim women approach counsellors after the pronouncement of *talaq*, when they have either been evicted from their marital home after an argument in which the husband pronounced *talaq* or have already been residing at their natal home for quite some time and then receive a legal notice, text message / letter, phone call there. The counsellors try and reconcile the couple if the *iddat* period has not expired. If the husband is cooperative even if the *iddat* period has concluded they may get him to wed his ex-wife again with a fresh *nikah* and *mehr*.

However in most cases, husbands do not even respond to counsellor's phone calls/ text messages/ postal notices, home visits prove futile and divorced wives are then forced to consider cumbersome, expensive, prolonged and often inconclusive formal legal action. Further, the widespread media coverage of the criminalisation of triple *talaq* has made men wary of pronouncing *talaq*, unfortunately, they now seem to prefer plain abandonment (Khan, 2021; Sengupta & Akbar, 2021).

Given the scenario, especially in light of the ongoing legal challenges to even *talaq hasan* ("Supreme Court agrees to examine validity", 2023) the

Supreme Court guidelines in *Shamim Ara* (often obeyed more in letter than in spirit) mandating pre-divorce mediation offer an excellent opportunity to include Muslim women in the process of terminating a marriage via *talaq* (*Shamim Ara v. State of U.P. & Anr.*, 2002).

- iii. **Khula.** One would be hard-pressed to find a concept within Muslim personal law as misunderstood as *khula*. Variousy touted, no doubt by well-meaning politicians, academics and even judges as an embodiment of Muslim women's empowerment, as an undeniable right, equivalent to the unilateral extra-judicial *talaq* available to a Muslim husband and a shining exemplar of gender justice and equality in Islam (Asbi K N v Hashim MU, 2021; "Muslim women can", 2023; "Only Family Courts can", 2023; Prasad, 2022; Shamshad & Mohammad, 2021; X and Others v. Y and Others 2021) *khula*, as it operates in reality on the ground requires the consent of the husband and necessitates financial consequences, if the woman is very lucky, only foregoing *mehr* and *iddat* maintenance.

At present the realm of *khula* is where most Muslim women wield influence when it comes to their involvement in counselling and marital dispute resolution. Were *khula* to be an absolute right there would simply be no need for their skilful negotiation and persuasion to get the husband to sign on the *khula* papers. The woman would only have to send the requisite legal papers offering a *khula* and the husband would be obliged to reply with a notice accepting the offer and hence terminating their *nikah*. That is not the case.

As it occurs *khula* involves a Muslim woman seeking to exit a marriage where the husband is usually at fault, mostly unable to financially maintain her or physically violent/ emotionally abusive. In an ideal world, such a circumstance would not lead to a *khula* but a *faskh* where subject to the wife proving the fault the *qazi* would dissolve the *nikah* without the consent of the husband and require him to pay outstanding *mehr* and maintenance. The presence of a *qazi* and a functioning *darul qaza / shariah* court would mean that *khula* then would be required largely in cases where a Muslim woman was seeking a no-fault divorce, perhaps owing to incompatibility and hence would offer some form of financial compensation to the blameless and unwilling husband to persuade him to free her from the marital bond.

Muslim women seeking to free themselves from a *nikah* spend years and considerable amounts of money to secure a valid *khula* (Vatuk, 2019). Genuine female activists, lawyers and counsellors play a huge role in providing much-needed advice and free aid to such women (Jones, 2019), usually in cooperation with a similarly-minded mufti or *qazi* (Dutta, 2022). While Islamic law fixes a limit to the financial consideration that needs to

be offered in reality middlemen and brokers, family members of the husband or even the woman herself not to mention lawyers and sometimes *qazis* see it as an opportunity for extortion. In situations where the husband not merely refuses to show up at the counselling centre or *darul qaza* but has cut off all communication, moved to another country and/or cannot be traced, the question of getting him to sign the *khula* papers and release his wife from the *nikah* does not arise. Such a Muslim wife is left hanging and cannot remarry (Norton & Ahmed, 2016). This is why it is vital for Muslim women to have the option of approaching a *darul qaza* to demand a *faskh*.

- iv. ***Faskh***. The termination of a Muslim marriage via *faskh* primarily involves the dissolution of the marriage by a *qazi*. To be able to effect such a dissolution the *qazi* must by virtue of his training be religiously qualified to do so. Not anyone can become a *qazi* and wield the authority and power to dissolve a *nikah* by *faskh*. At a minimum, such a person must be a mufti (“Maharashtra government”, 2020). In India, the *Imarat Shariah* Bihar, Odisha & Jharkhand located at Pulwari Sharif, Patna has a long-running course that trains *qazis* (Darul Quaza, Imarat Shariah, n.d.) and most *Darul Qazas* managed by the All India Muslim Personal Law Board are manned by religiously qualified *qazis*. Note that it is permitted for Muslim women to become *muftiahs* and therefore they would technically be eligible for the *qazi* training programme as well.

Faskh requires the petitioner to put forth evidence to prove their claim and also requires proving fault. While the Dissolution of Muslim Marriages Act 1939 covers grounds for divorce traditionally available under *faskh*, the glaring problem is that it does not mandate the appointment of a religiously qualified Muslim person to preside over the case. Worse the Act is interpreted in a way that puts dissolution via *faskh* within the exclusive jurisdiction of secular courts. This has meant that Muslim women who wish to obtain a *faskh* cannot do so outside court. Were they to proceed to a *darul qaza* for dissolution even if they manage to obtain a decree / order / judgement in their favour dissolving the *nikah* it has no value in court and cannot be used as proof of divorce to meet official requirements (Sureshkumar, 2017).

Further even if such women manage to go to court and successfully secure an official decree via the infinitely more expensive and time consuming route available under the DMMA, the fact that the judge is not a religiously qualified Muslim makes the decree invalid. Muslim society does not accept it and such women have difficulty getting remarried because prospective suitors and their families believe the woman’s former *nikah* persists and therefore it is not permissible under Islamic Law for another man to marry her.

Depriving Muslim women of an extra-judicial *faskh* available through a *darul qaza* and forcing them to bring a suit in court under the DMMA is an anti-women stance and ought to be remedied at the earliest. This is because it forces Muslim women to obtain a *khula* and suffer financial loss when it is not required and when the husband neither pronounces *talaq* nor refuses to consent to a *khula* or goes missing, leaving her hanging. This while the permissibility of polygyny within both Islamic and Indian law leaves the husband free to marry other women and move on with life.

- v. **Talaq-e-Tafweez.** In the absence of a *darul qaza* with the powers to effect a *faskh* considered valid by the Indian judiciary unconditional *talaq-e-tafweez* where the right to pronounce a divorce upon herself is delegated to the wife (Carroll, 1982) is ideal, since no third party is involved. However a more acceptable solution for the socially conservative might mean that the right to pronounce a divorce may be delegated to a state recognised *darul qaza* or arbitration centre instead of the wife (Yaseen, 2016). Needless to say as discussed earlier such a state recognised *darul qaza* or arbitration centre will by law include Muslim women on its panel. Muslim women as female *qazis* would also have a massive role to play in popularising and incorporating the *tafweez* clause in *nikahnamas*.

5. Issues related to securing a religiously/socially accepted and legally valid divorce and obtaining an officially recognised legal document

A refusal on the part of state authorities to recognize the widespread socially and religiously accepted valid forms of divorce and their persistence in insisting such divorces have no consequence means more trouble for Muslim women (Salam, 2022). Those divorced orally without witnesses or any documentary evidence are unable to have a divorce certificate issued by the Waqf Board and this has serious consequences for their ability to claim government pension for divorcees, remarry, claim child custody or secure valid documents such as passports for themselves and their children. A vast majority of these women also do not have the resources to approach courts to prove their case and have a decree issued declaring their marital status.

In Telangana the practice of issuing certificates as proof of divorce can be traced back to an agreement between a private association of *qazis*, *Anjuman-e-Qazath* and the government run state Waqf Board in 1973. This is an arrangement peculiar to the state and as with the rules governing the eligibility of a *qazi* and procedure of appointment of government *qazis*, and the format, printing and distribution of *nikahnamas*, the practice of issuing divorce certificates and registering divorces also varies widely from state to state across India.

While the inability to secure valid proof of divorce and an official document certifying the same has always been a problem it is particularly acute after the enactment of the Muslim Women (Protection of Rights on Marriage) Act, 2019. Greater public awareness about *talaq* and scrutiny over the legality of various modes of *talaq* in India suddenly put the *Qazzath* section in a spot. In the absence of any legislation stating the procedure for issuing a divorce certificate and vesting power to do so in the *Qazzath* section housed in the Waqf Board, the practice of the Waqf Board issuing divorce certificates without clear legal sanction came under question. Pre-empting trouble the Waqf Board initially stopped issuing all divorce certificates; later on it re-continued issuing *khula* certificates (Mohammed, 2021; Moin, 2019b; “Why is Qazat system under threat”, 2023).

Worryingly the criminalisation of triple *talaq* even as it is held to have no consequence has led to Muslim husbands refusing to pronounce any kind of *talaq*, husbands are either forcing wives trapped in abusive marriages to seek *khula* (Akbar, 2021; Moin, 2019a; Sadam, 2023) or in many cases simply abandoning them (Ara, 2020; Khan, 2022; Parveen, 2023). Women who fail to secure a *khula* are left hanging, unable to remarry as their marriage persists. This grim situation is a direct violation of God’s command in the *Quran* that believing men either live with their wives in kindness or part with them honourably (The Qur’an, 65:2). Even more disturbing is the fact that desperate Muslim women, some victims of severe domestic violence are being forced to withdraw perfectly valid and genuine criminal cases against their husbands in exchange for a *khula*. They literally barter justice for freedom. The absence of extra-judicial *faskh* that would allow a Muslim woman to exit the marriage without the consent of her husband is largely responsible for this horrific situation.

Note that it is common practice to file maintenance and domestic violence cases in court to build pressure on unwilling husbands to show up at the negotiating table and sign the *khula* papers. This does not mean that the cases are ‘false’ or undeserving it only means that the woman’s primary intent is to free herself from the marital bond as soon as possible not to pursue the case over several years to its logical conclusion. As a legal strategy, this is popular despite mixed results for stubborn men take greater offence at being ‘harassed’ by police and court summons and become even more determined to not assent to a *khula*. Muslim husbands who have the resources and networks at their disposal to ‘manage’ the police and fund protracted legal battles in courts are perfectly content to bide their time and seemingly derive great satisfaction from torturing their wives. The lack of any meaningful regulation of polygyny also allows such men to marry more women while preventing their wives from exiting the marriage and marrying someone else.

6. Setting up a Muslim Mediation, Arbitration and Reconciliation Centre (MARC)

Given the existing realities on the ground establishing a formal institution to deal with Muslim marital disputes such as a Muslim Mediation, Arbitration and Reconciliation Centre (MARC) with a specified gender ratio linked to the Family Court system would certainly be a game-changing move. The MARC could function as an autonomous institution set up by the respective state governments and would offer an acceptable midway solution to the thorny issue of a uniform civil code. In all likelihood such a centre would be backed by the ulema (The Message Media, 2021, 1:52:24) and supported by the community, embodying the Law Commission of India's preference for progressive internal reforms (Law Commission of India, 2018).

A MARC should ideally be brought into existence via legislation and also formally linked to various government departments to make it as efficient and effective as possible. Item no 5. under List III in the Seventh Schedule Constitution of India includes "marriage and divorce" and therefore state governments have the power to legislate on this concurrent subject. In addition to the Family Courts (Ahmed & Chircop, 2017), Court and District Legal Services Authority run mediation centres, the Muslim arbitration centre should be linked with existing one-stop crisis centres run in collaboration with the Department of Police and the Department of Women and Child Welfare and NRI Cells. Also, the Centre must be linked with the state Waqf Board given that waqf boards in India are legally responsible for financially maintaining destitute divorcees not supported by male family members (Rizwan, 2014; The Muslim Women Protection of Rights on Divorce Act, 1986, Sec. 4(2)).

The MARC panel handling cases ought to consist of government-appointed qazis (who are also trained muftis), lawyers, doctors, counsellors and social workers. While realistically it might take us a decade or more to train Muslim women to become *muftiahs* and attain the requisite qualifications to be eligible for appointment as a *qazi* competent to dissolve a Muslim marriage via *faskh* Muslim women trained in secular vocations will always be eligible to be appointed to other positions on the panel.

This is already happening at several bodies across India where Muslim women are working alongside mufti's. While the mufti of course by virtue of his religious knowledge and expertise is recognised as the authority and expected to make the final decision (particularly in cases of *faskh*) women are actively involved at all stages of the entire process. Their opinions are given serious weight by mufti's and they do have significant influence over the final decision arrived at.

Telangana already has a very unique hybrid institution in the Marriage Counselling Centre for Minorities functioning at the Haj House in Hyderabad (Marriage Council Center, Telangana State Waqf Board, n.d.; S.K.M., 2015). Set up by executive order in 2015 with the express mandate of resolving marital disputes “in light of the legal provisions and respective personal law, if any”, the panel along with a senior mufti and a government qazi at the time of inception included two women members as well, a lawyer and a representative of a Muslim women’s religious organisation (Minorities Welfare (EST.II) Department, 2015). The centre, though successful to a degree, is merely a counselling body and has been severely hampered by the inability to summon husbands in particular, being vested with no powers by law to do so and is unable to come to the aid of Muslim women abandoned by their husbands. Despite the presence of both a mufti and government *qazi* the panel is in no position to dissolve a *nikah via faskh*.

Telangana incidentally is also home to the International Arbitration and Mediation Centre (IAMC), a project backed fully by the state government. In his inaugural address the then Chief Justice of India N. V. Ramana put forth the possibility of the centre handling family disputes as well (“First Case at IAMC”, 2021). Should political will and public opinion crystallise on the matter the state is certainly uniquely situated to be a pioneer in securing the welfare and rights of its female Muslim residents via innovative institutional solutions.

Country and state-wide statistics are hard to come by but even a modest estimate would suggest that within the city of Hyderabad alone there are hundreds if not thousands of women left hanging by their husbands with no recourse to justice. Alleviating their suffering would require formulating practical solutions that would enable them to secure a speedy and affordable divorce that is both religiously valid and officially recognised. The real value of a government-recognised MARC would lie in the facilitation of *faskh* via arbitration. Arbitrators could step in and release women from a bad marriage where the husband is unwilling or absent. The inclusion of women in the arbitration panel would enable them to fulfil this urgent need to assist ‘hanging’ Muslim women seeking to exit abusive marriages.

7. Conclusion

While one cannot deny the symbolic as well as transformative significance of a self-styled female *qazi* officiating a *nikah* ceremony (especially in terms of keeping the issue alive and facilitating difficult yet vital conversations on socio-cultural practices and norms) and even as one fully recognises the vital work being done by Muslim women ‘*qazis*’ in various women run organisations across India concerning marital counselling and dispute resolution we all need to understand that the revolutionary potential of a

female *qazi* is realised when she either heads or is part of a government recognised arbitration centre that is endowed with actual powers to effect an extra-judicial *faskh* and to issue an official document that is recognised by the courts. The empowerment of Muslim women in India cannot be divorced from this reality. Any solution that falls short of this will keep them running from pillar to post to secure not just a valid divorce but any semblance of justice.

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